

Shockley diode (Dinistor) with integrated control

Fisenko Aleksey Leonidovich
design engineer PJSC "ELECTROVIPRYAMITEL"
(Saransk, Mordovia, Russia)
fisenkoalexfox@gmail.com, fisenkoal1985@mail.ru
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Currently, modern pulse technologies in power electronics are being widely developed, production technologies are being optimized and switches for powerful, rapidly increasing current pulses are being improved. Of great interest are those developed at the Physicotechnical Institute. A.F. Ioffe reversibly-connected dynistor (RCD), dynistors with deep levels (DLD), shock-ionized dynistor (SID) [1].

Known dinistor (Patent No. RU197597 for invention "Dinistor" // Publ. 05/15/2020) [1], which is a four-layer $p^+ - n - p - n^+$ -structure with an anode p^+ emitter and a cathode n^+ emitter, which are shorted by shunts with integrated reverse diodes. The known dinistor switches to a high-conductivity state in a few nanoseconds. Switching occurs due to a sudden overvoltage with a rise rate of at least 1 kV/ns.

With nanosecond current pulses, the skin effect has a great influence on the uniformity of switching of the dinistor, due to which the structure switches unevenly over the area [3]. It is also possible to localize the current in a small area with a smaller base width due to uneven grinding operations of the semiconductor wafer, due to defects in the structure and due to uneven diffusion.

Therefore, the presence of a control area (control in the center of the structure and with possible branching over the area) will allow the dinistor to switch evenly over the entire area. The patent (Patent No. RU2697874 for the utility model "Reversibly-connected dynistor with integrated control" // Publ. 08/21/2019) [4] already presents the structure of a dynistor with integrated control RCDT (Reversible dynistor with integrated control), but it is intended for RCD structures, which switches as a result of reversing the blocked voltage and passing a short pulse of control current through the built-in system of reverse conduction channels. Wherein in the central region of the diode-thyristor there is an asymmetric thyristor with a regenerative control electrode. For a dynistor with an integrated control area, a diode structure under the control area is required for overvoltage switching (to block the switching of the dinistor structure under the control area); It is also possible to use an RCDT, but to reduce the dU/dt effect under the control area, a shunted structure is required (dinistor with an integrated shunted control area).

Further in the article, possible options for the control region of the dinistor structure in the cross section are presented:

- Fig.1 – Dinistor with integrated control straight polarity, with one control stage;
- Fig.2 – Dinistor with integrated control reverse polarity, with one control stage;
- Fig.3 – Dinistor with integrated control straight polarity, with two control stages;
- Fig.4 – Dinistor with integrated control reverse polarity, with two control stages;
- Fig.5 – Dinistor with an integrated shunted control area straight polarity, with two control stages;
- Fig.6 – Dinistor with an integrated shunted control area reverse polarity, with two control stages.

Fig.1

Fig.2

Fig.3

Fig.4

Fig.5

Fig.6

The control structure of this dinistor (Dinistor with integrated control) is taken from the well-known thyristor structure [5,6,7] and RCDDT [4].

Shunts are located on the anode and cathode of the dinistor - they form an $n^+ - n - p - p^+$ diode structure. Shunts are known in the thyristor structure in the form of circles [7], there are in the form of squares (the diode part of the dinistor structure) [2], and there are also descriptions of shunts with the shape of hexagons and polyhedral [6,8,9,10]. The most preferable option would be a hexagonal diode $n^+ - n - p - p^+$ -structure.

The operating principle of a dinistor with an integrated control system is similar to a SID or DLD: voltage is applied to the anode (A) and cathode (K) (the dinistor is in the closed state); the difference is that a dinistor with an integrated control system has a control electrode (GATE) and a control current (pulse or constant) is supplied to it with a polarity in accordance with the figures; this current is not sufficient to open the dinistor, but is necessary for the flow and accumulation of charges in near-surface structure between the control electrode (GATE) and the cathode; then the voltage (overvoltage) increases sharply with a rise rate of at least 1 kV/ns, as a result of which the dinistor switches.

The main difference between a dinistor with a built-in control system and a SID, RCD and DLD is that a dinistor with a built-in control system begins switching from the control zone and thereby eliminates the skin effect for overvoltage pulses with a nanosecond rise, and also with branched control, the dinistor switching becomes more uniform over the entire area.

A dinistor with an integrated control system, by analogy with an RCDDT (reversibly-connected dynistor with integrated control), can be called a DLDT (dynistors with deep levels with integrated control) or SIDT (shock-ionized dynistor with integrated control).

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